

MAPPING INTERIOR DEFORMATION OF COMPOSITES USING DIGITAL VOLUMETRIC SPECKLE PHOTOGRAPHY

Fu-pen Chiang¹ and Lingtao Mao^{1, 2}

¹ Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Stony Brook University,
Stony Brook, NY 11794-2300, USA

Email: fu-pen.chiang@stonybrook.edu, web page: <http://www.stonybrook.edu>

² State Key Laboratory of Coal Resources and Safe Mining(China University of Mining & Technology)
D11, Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing 100083, China

Email: mlt@cumtb.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.cumtb.edu.cn>

Keywords: 3D Speckle, Composite Beam Internal Strain Field, Digital Speckle Photography, Digital Image Correlation

ABSTRACT

The 3D deformation field of an interior longitudinal section of a composite beam under three-point bending has been mapped using the newly developed technique called Digital Volumetric Speckle Photography (DVSP). The technique employs a Micro X-ray CT system to record a volume image of the specimen and treats the composite beam's internal texture as 3D volumetric speckles. By extending the algorithm used in 2D speckle photography into 3D we are able to calculate the internal strain field quantitatively. Full field maps of u , v and w are obtained which allow the computation of strain fields. We observed that the first principle strain distribution is a good predictor for the impending failure of the beam.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials, be its fiber reinforced, particle reinforced, woven, etc., are three dimensional in nature. Analytical or numerical analysis of their behaviour under load is an extremely complicated endeavour. Various theoretical and numerical approaches have been proposed to analyze the deformation mechanism of composites [1-11]. Most of them involve the concept of volumetric unit cell (VUC) which is assumed to represent a typical volumetric element that is anywhere and everywhere in the composite. This is the so-called homogenization scheme. After many complicated mathematical analyses and numerical plotting of various load-response curves, the test for the validity of the model is universally performed on a simple tension coupon. More sophisticated ones use a 2D plane tester. Evaluation of the material damage is either by visual observation, ultrasonic penetration, or flash x-ray radiogram. All these techniques can only reveal either the surface, or averaged through thickness information. And they are all gross information at best. The inadequacy of these modelling approaches and inspection techniques are obvious and well recognized. But the lack of experimental tools to probe the interior of a composite has left a void in the intellectual modelling community. As a result, design engineers are reluctant to use these models to design composite structures. Even when they do, a large safety factor is incorporated. Thus, there is an urgent and longstanding need to have a technique to probe the interior of composite material/structure to evaluate their 3D deformation characteristics. It is only then that a sound theoretical model can be constructed. In the follow we shall introduce a new technique whereby we can probe the interior deformation of any composites and a theory developed to utilize the interior texture as 3D speckles to analyze the 3D deformation field of the composite under various loading conditions.

2 DIGITAL VOLUMETRIC SPECKLE PHOTOGRAPHY(DVSP) – A NEW TECHNIQUE OF 3D STRESS/STRAIN ANALYSIS

In the field of experimental stress analysis, the ultimate goal has always been to find a technique that can probe the interior deformation of any solid material. In the 50's and 60's, stress frozen photoelasticity, scattered light photoelasticity, and later integrated photoelasticity techniques were developed [12-14]. They all require the model material to be birefringent and transparent. Later came the development of moiré and speckle methods [4]. While the need for birefringent material is eliminated in these newer techniques, the material still needs to be transparent. The application of all these techniques to composites is limited at best. For example, photoelasticity (2D & 3D) is only used to probe stress field around a single fiber (or a few fibers at most). In the following, we shall describe a new 3D technique that can probe interior deformation of real composite material/structures from a 360 degree angle.

2.1. The 2D Speckle Photography Technique

The speckle technique can be traced to a 1968 paper by J. Burch [15]. But the major development is in the 70's and 80's [16-19]. Originally traditional photography is used. With the advent of digital camera and fast computer; a digital version is developed [20-21] which has become a ubiquitous tool in experimental stress analysis. The use of a random pattern of speckles for quantitative measurement constitutes a major milestone in the art of experimental strain analysis. Heretofore, a regular pattern (be it a grid, a ruler, a geometric pattern) is used as the measuring gauge. Its deviation from the norm under load is used as a measure of strain. With speckle photography, a random pattern of dots and marks are used as the measuring tool. Instead of following the movement of individual speckles under load, a cluster of particle's movement is tracked by correlation calculation. (It should be noted that in the digital image correlation method, correlation is performed at the spatial domain whereas in digital speckle photography technique, correlation is performed at the transform domain after a Fourier transform is performed on the before and after load speckle patterns. Because of the computational efficiency of FFT (Fast Fourier Transform), the computation time using this approach is 40X faster than that of direct correlation calculation). In the following we shall describe how this technique is extended into the 3D domain.

2.2 Theory of 3D Digital Volumetric Speckle Photography (DVSP)

The afore mentioned speckle photography technique is essentially a 2D plane technique in that one can only analyze one plane (a few at most with difficulty) and this plane is mostly a surface plane. Although by using embedded speckles inside the material, an interior plane of a transparent material can be interrogated. But the procedure is so complicated that it has few practical applications.

What we propose to do in this project is to develop a 3D volumetric speckle technique using the volumetric imaging capability of a Micro CT (CAT scan). The principle of Micro-CT is identical to that of medical CT, except it is smaller and in general is not used in the medical field. X-ray is also used as the light source which can penetrate most materials. And most materials contain impurities that when recorded can serve as 3D volumetric speckles. The theory of the digital volumetric speckle photography is schematically shown in Fig. 1.

Digital volume images of a 3D solid before and after deformation are reconstructed from a Micro-CT recording. These two volume images are defined as reference volume image and deformed volume image, respectively. They are then divided into subsets with voxel arrays of $32 \times 32 \times 32$ voxels, for example, and 'compared'. The result is a displacement vector representing the collective movement experienced by all the speckles within the subset. Based on the theory of 2D digital speckle photography technique, the DVSP principle is described as follows:

Let $h_1(x,y,z)$ and $h_2(x,y,z)$ be the complex amplitudes of the light disturbance of a generic speckle subset pair, before and after deformation, respectively, and

$$h_2(x, y, z) = h_1 [x - u(x, y, z), y - v(x, y, z), z - w(x, y, z)] \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Schematics demonstrating the processing algorithm of DVSP

where u , v and w are the displacement components experienced by the speckles along the x , y and z directions respectively. A first-step 3D FFT is applied to both h_1 and h_2 yielding

$$\begin{aligned} H_1(f_x, f_y, f_z) &= \mathfrak{F}\{h_1(x, y, z)\} \\ H_2(f_x, f_y, f_z) &= \mathfrak{F}\{h_2(x, y, z)\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $H_1(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ is the Fourier transform of $h_1(x, y, z)$, $H_2(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ is the Fourier transform of $h_2(x, y, z)$ and \mathfrak{F} stands for Fourier Transform.

Then, a numerical interference between the two 3D speckle patterns is performed at the spectral domain, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} F(f_x, f_y, f_z) &= \frac{H_1(f_x, f_y, f_z)H_2^*(f_x, f_y, f_z)}{\sqrt{|H_1(f_x, f_y, f_z)H_2(f_x, f_y, f_z)|}} \\ &\approx |H_1(f_x, f_y, f_z)| \exp\{j[\phi_1(f_x, f_y, f_z) - \phi_2(f_x, f_y, f_z)]\} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_1(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ and $\phi_2(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ are the phases of $H_1(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ and $H_2(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ respectively. And $*$ stands for the complex conjugate. It is seen that

$$\phi_1(f_x, f_y, f_z) - \phi_2(f_x, f_y, f_z) = 2\pi(uf_x + vf_y + wf_z) \quad (4)$$

Finally, the function is obtained by performing another 3D FFT resulting

$$G(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = \mathfrak{F}\{F(f_x, f_y, f_z)\} = \bar{G}(\xi - u, \eta - v, \zeta - w) \quad (5)$$

which is an expanded impulse function located at (u, v, w) . This process is carried out for every corresponding pair of subsets. By detecting the crest of this impulse function, an array of displacement vectors at each and every subset are obtained, from which strain tensors can be calculated using an appropriate strain-displacement relation. A software based on this theory is developed and is hereafter referred to as CASI-3D.

Based on this approach, the deformation of the subset itself is neglected. Because of the discrete nature of digital volume images, the displacements evaluated from equation (5) are integer multiples of one voxel. In order to obtain more accurate and sensitive characterization, a sub-voxel investigation of the crest position is desired. Surrounding the integer voxel of the crest, a cubic subset with size of

$3 \times 3 \times 3$ voxels is selected, a spline interpolation is employed to obtain the sub-voxel accuracy in this work.

3 APPLICATION OF DVSP TO INTERIOR MEASUREMENT OF COMPOSITES DEFORMATION

When applied to composite material the first issue is whether or not the Micro-CT can capture the minute interior details of a composite material. We secured a piece of composite material from the blade of a windmill as shown in Fig. 2 (a), which is taken with a conventional 35mm camera. It was scanned using a Micro-CT and a cubic element of the recorded volumetric is cropped from the stored data as shown in Fig. 2 (b). Three orthogonal sections through the cubic element are displayed in Fig. 3. It can be seen that all the details of the composite have been captured. The marks, defects, fiber boundaries can all be served speckles and they are sufficient for CASI-3D calculation. We proceeded to test whether or not we can obtain enough clear information to compute the interior strain field. We cut a thick prismatic beam from the composite and loaded it under three-point bend.

Figure 2. Composite block (a) conventional photography, (b) reconstructed CT image

Figure 3. Three orthogonal cross sections of the composite block from Fig. 2 (b)

The dimensions of the specimen is 38.5 (L), 18.8 (H) and 9.0 (T) mm, respectively. The load was applied incrementally in 11 steps as shown in Fig. 4. Maximum load recorded was at step 10 at 10.5 kN. Further loading resulted in failure at step 11.

At each and every load step the volumetric image of the specimen was recorded using a micro-CT as shown in Fig. 5. The recording was 360° allowing us to view any desired section. We selected the mid-section of the beam to do the following analysis. We calculated the 3D displacement fields u, v

and w of the midsection at each load step and the displacement fields along $z=4.5\text{mm}$ are displayed in Fig.6 and 7, respectively. Fig. 8 displayed the deformation field of the last load step 10 at 10.5 kN. There is no visible sign of impending failure that was to come when the load was further increased. The gray image of the section along $z=4.5\text{mm}$ in the specimen at load step 10 is also depicted in Fig. 8. There was no visible sign of impending failure either. However, when we calculated the strain distributions of the midsection at load step 10 (see Fig. 9), strain concentration as clearly indicated in various locations. The distribution of the first principal strain ϵ_1 correlates fairly well with the final failure pattern as marked by the corresponding ellipses shown.

Figure 4. Composite beam specimen and load/displacement curve.

Figure 5. The Micro-CT system used to record the volumetric image of the specimen at each loading step

Figure 6. 3D displacement distribution of the mid-section of the beam at (a) load step 6: 6.6 kN
(b) load step 7: 7.4 kN

Figure 7. 3D displacement distribution of the midsection of the beam at (a) load steps 8: 8.3KN
(b) load step 9: 9.3KN

Figure 8. Deformation fields of the last load step before failure.

Figure 9. Strain fields of the midsection at load step (10) and failure (step11)

4 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

We have demonstrated the newly developed DVSP technique can indeed be applied to probe the interior deformation of composites. Apparently the markings on the CT image resulting from fibers, impurities within the material, and the micro voids created by the manufacturing process are sufficient to be treated as 3D speckles. And the DVSP technique we developed has been shown to be very effective to give quantitative information of the interior strain distribution anywhere in the material. The DVSP is a game changing technique in the art of 3D experimental mechanics. More research is needed to evaluate its accuracy, precision and resolution. And its application is not limited to composites. In a prior work we have demonstrated that it can be effectively applied to probe the interior deformation of rocks. We foresee its future application to biology and medical sciences as well.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was financially supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (51374211), National key foundation for exploring scientific instrument of China (2013YQ240803), Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (2009QM02) and the Laboratory for Experimental Mechanic Research of the Department of Mechanical Engineering at Stony Brook University. F.P.Chiang wishes to thank Dr. Yapa Rajapakse, Director of the US Office of Naval Research's Solid Mechanics Program for his support over the years for advancement of the speckle technique.

REFERENCES

- [1] D.H. Allen, D.C. Lagoudes (eds) *Damage Mechanics in Composites*, ASME AMD-Vol. 150, AD-Vol. 32, 1992.
- [2] M.M Shokrieh, and M. Zakeri, "Generalized technique for cumulative damage modeling of composite laminates," *J Composite Materials*, 2007, 41: 2643-2656.
- [3] H.K. Lee, and S.H. Pyo, "3D-damage model for fiber-reinforced brittle composites with microcracks and imperfect interfaces," *J ENG MECH-ASCE*, 2009, 135(10).
- [4] T.E. Tay, G. Liu, and V.B. C. Tan, "Damage progression in open-hole tension laminates by the SIFT-EFM approach. *J Composite Material*, 2006, 40: 971-992.
- [5] R. Talreja, "Multi-scale modeling in damage mechanics of composite materials," *J. Material Science*, 2006, 41(20):6800-6812.
- [6] J. Varna, R. Talreja, "Integration of macro- and micro- damage mechanics for the performance evaluation of composite material," *Mech of Composite Materials*, 2012, 48(2):145-160.
- [7] J. Lua, C.T. Key, et al, "Rate dependent multicontinuum progressive failure analysis of woven fabric composites structures under dynamic impact," *Shock and Vibration*, 2004, 11(2):103-117.
- [8] L.P. Khroshun, E.N. Shikula, "Micromechanics of long-term damage of particulate composites with unlimited microdurability," *Int. Appl. Mech.*, 2008, 44(11):1202-1212.
- [9] A. Bezazi, A. Mahi, J.-M. Bethelot, and B. Bezzazi, "Experimental analysis of behavior and damage of sandwich composite materials in three-point bending. Part 2. Fatigue test results and damage mechanisms," *Strength of Materials*, 2009, 41(3):257.
- [10] A. Tabiei, I. Ivanov, "Micro-Mechanical Model with strain rate dependency and damage for impact simulation of woven fabric composite," *Mech Adv Mater Struc*, 2007, 14 (5): 365-377.
- [11] U. Santhosh, J. Ahmad, "A model for estimated nonlinear deformation and damage in ceramic matrix composites," *J. Composite Materials*, 2013, 47.
- [12] R. L. Burguete, and E. A. Patterson, "A photoelastic study of contact between a cylinder and a half-space," *Exp. Mech.*, 1997 37(3):314-313.
- [13] Dupre, J. C, Lagarde, A., "Photoelastic analysis of a three-dimensional specimen by optical slicing and digital image processing," *Exp. Mech*, 1997, 37:393-397.

- [14] T.Kihara, "Whole-field measurement of three-dimensional stress by scattered-light photoelasticity with unpolarized light," 14th International Conference on Experimental Mechanics, 2010, 6:32006.
- [15] J.M.,Burch, and J.M.J.,Tokarski, "Production of multiple beam fringes from photographic scatters," *Opt. Acta.* 1968, 15:101-111.
- [16] F. P,Chiang, and A,Asundi, "Interior displacement and strain measurement using white light speckles," *App. Opt.*,1980, 19: 2254-2256.
- [17] J.A.,Leendertz, "Interferometric displacement measurements on scattering surface utilizing speckle effect," *J. Phys. E* , 1970, 3:214-218.
- [18] F.P. Chiang, and A. Asundi, "White light speckle method of experimental strain analysis, *App. Opt.*," 1979, 18(4): 409-411.
- [19] F.P.,Chiang, and F. Jin, "A New Technique Using Digital Speckle Correlation for Nondestructive Inspection of Corrosion," *Material Evaluation*, 1997, 55(7): 813-816.
- [20] D.J. Chen, and F.P. Chiang, "Computer-aided speckle interferometry using spectral amplitude fringes," *App. Opt.*, 1993, 32(2):225-236.
- [21] D.J. Chen, F.P.Chiang, Y.S.Tan, et al, "Digital speckle-displacement measurement using a complex spectrum method," *App. Opt.*, 1993, 32(11):1839-1849.